

Integrating terrain knowledge into point cloud simplification for terrain modelling

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Abstract—Terrain models are widely used to depict the shape of the Earth's surface. With the development of photogrammetric methods, point cloud data have become one of the most popular data sources for terrain modelling. However, the obtained point clouds are of high density, which often increases redundancy rather than improving accuracy. Therefore, point cloud simplification should be a core component of terrain modelling. This paper proposes a point cloud simplification method by integrating terrain knowledge into terrain modelling (TKPCS). The method contains two steps: (1) terrain knowledge intuition and construction and (2) point cloud simplification using this terrain knowledge for terrain modelling. The proposed approach is benchmarked against improved versions of existing methods to validate its capability and accuracy in digital elevation model construction and terrain derivative extraction. The results show that the simplified points of the TKPCS method can generate finer resolution terrain models with higher accuracy and greater information entropy. The good performance of the TKPCS method is also stable at different scales. This work endeavors to transform perceptive terrain knowledge into a process of point cloud simplification and can benefit future research related to terrain modelling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Earth's surface consists of multiple landforms and a wide range of topographic characteristics [1]. Terrain modelling and subsequent analysis can help recognize and explore the character and formation of the Earth's surface [2]. At present, point cloud data are widely used for terrain modelling [3]. Developments in measurement technology have led to easier acquisition of high-density point cloud data. However, such point clouds introduce new problems concerning postprocessing redundancy for terrain modelling and analysis. Furthermore, terrain data should match the scale of the process mechanism and analysis purpose of geoscience research. Terrain data-related studies do not need to be carried out at decimetre- and millimetre-scale resolutions [4]. For example, accurate slope calculation and water flow simulation can be achieved at the metre level. Therefore, it is necessary to simplify point clouds.

Many studies have focused on point cloud simplification and the methods can be divided into mesh-based and point cloud-based. Mesh-based simplification methods initially build regular meshes based on point clouds and then simplify them using a given rule [5-6]. However, mesh-based methods are limited by the large computational cost of mesh generation. Point cloud-based methods [7-9], for example cluster-based simplification, directly simplify point clouds without constructing polygonal meshes. The point clouds are first clustered into local point sets which are then simplified based on user defined rules. However, due to the limitations of clustering algorithms, the simplified result points are not suitable for terrain modelling.

Whether the mesh-based or point cloud-based method is used, the point information should always be considered during the simplification process. Normally, the geometric curvature, curvature combined with entropy, and the deviation of the normal vectors were commonly used as indicators to describe the importance of points [7-9]. However, although these indicators can show the significance of points on a local surface from a geometric view, a terrain surface consists of complex topographic characteristics, and traditional indicators are insufficient for the retention of terrain feature points after point cloud simplification.

Previous approaches have produced good simplifications of the point clouds of regular objects. However, a terrain surface is characterized by abrupt change, gradual change, and constant morphology [10] and is so complex that it is beyond the application of existing methods. At present, high-density terrain point cloud data simplification methods mainly include traditional curvature, random, and uniform methods. However, complex terrain features such as slope and land surface curvatures are not fully considered in existing simplification methods. Furthermore, terrain information consists of global structural and local detailed features [11], and both should be considered in simplifying terrain point clouds.

The global and local characteristics can be summarized as the understanding and intuition of terrain knowledge, which represents a combination of the perceptive descriptions of

topographic characteristics across different environments [1]. It consists of global and local terrain knowledge. In this paper, we propose a point cloud simplification method by integrating terrain knowledge into terrain modelling. This method first intuitively constructs the terrain knowledge of the point cloud, and then, based on the integrated terrain knowledge, we develop a simplification method to retain terrain feature points.

II. METHODS

A. Terrain knowledge institution and construction

In this paper, global terrain knowledge was used as the principle to extract global feature points, which can control the structure of the terrain, and local terrain knowledge was used as a basis to extract local feature points which can help to enrich the details of a terrain surface. Fig. 1(c) shows the simplified points, which consist of the global and local feature points.

1) Global terrain knowledge

The global structure of a terrain surface is constructed using terrain feature points and lines [1]. We recognized the global terrain feature information as global terrain knowledge to preserve global feature points, which can prevent the loss of global terrain feature points during local simplification process. Normally, the feature points and lines of the terrain surface mentioned above are mainly distributed at the locations of abrupt changes in terrain, which can be indicated by the profile curvature that is the curvature along the direction of the maximum slope gradient, and is the rate of change of the terrain slope. In this study, the profile curvature was used to construct global terrain knowledge to efficiently preserve global feature points.

Specifically, the profile curvature values in ascending order were divided into two categories using the Jenks natural breaks classification method. The points with higher curvature values were selected to form a candidate point set of global feature points. Then global terrain feature points can be obtained by uniformly sampling the global candidate point set with a specific reduction ratio (i.e., point cloud reduction ratio). The extracted global terrain feature points can control the basic structure of the terrain surface (Fig. 1(a)).

2) Local terrain knowledge

Local terrain points can enrich terrain details, ensure the relative uniformity of point distribution, and improve the accuracy of terrain modelling. Terrain derivatives can express the morphological features of landforms. In previous studies, terrain derivatives, such as slope, were chosen to optimize terrain features during DEM processing because they are critical to many analyses [11]. Furthermore, the combination of multiple terrain derivatives has been proved to be more suitable to describe the complexity and roughness of a terrain surface [12]. Thus, in this study, we chose multiple terrain derivatives, including the elevation standard deviation, total accumulation

curvature, and slope, to construct local terrain knowledge to control the simplification of the point cloud. These terrain derivatives consider both the terrain complexity and the material flow on the surface and ensure that the extracted points are representative of the local terrain surface (Fig. 1(b)).

The local terrain knowledge was constructed using the weighted summation of the terrain derivatives. Since the distribution of landforms often varies considerably at high, medium, and low altitudes (Fig. 1(d)), for weight setting, we divided the test area into three subregions to construct local terrain knowledge, respectively, because we believe that the weights should be different for subregions in different landforms. Specifically, the Jenks natural breaks method, which uses the elevation data of the test area as input, was used to divide the test area into three subregions of high, medium, and low altitudes to construct local terrain knowledge. Then, the weights of the terrain derivatives were determined using the criteria importance through the intercriteria correlation method (CRITIC) [13] in different subregions.

The terrain derivatives mentioned above were calculated on a local quadratic function fitted using the local point cloud by the moving least squares algorithm [14]. In addition, we used a multiscale method that computes robust geometric features on point clouds to retrieve the optimal neighbourhood size for each point [15] rather than commonly used fixed search radius or number of points.

Figure 1. (a) Global feature points. (b) Local feature points. (c) The combination of the global and local feature points. (d) A, B, and C are different landforms in high, middle, and low altitude regions. (e) Diagram of the roulette wheel selection method. (f), (g), and (h) are the raw point clouds, DEM, and rendering map of the test area, respectively.

B. Integrating terrain knowledge into point cloud simplification

The TKPCS method flowchart is shown in Fig. 2. The global terrain feature points were first obtained by uniformly sampling the global candidate point set. Then, the retained global terrain feature points were integrated into the local grid simplification process. The local terrain feature points were extracted using the local terrain knowledge within the grid, which can be divided into two steps. The first step is to grid the point cloud and determine the number of simplified points in each grid based on the number of points and their local terrain knowledge values within the grid relative to all grids. The second step is a grid-by-grid local simplification process controlled by the local terrain knowledge. The test area was first gridded into subregions. In each subregion, points were simplified according to the strength of the local terrain knowledge. The principle is that the greater the local terrain knowledge value of a point is, the greater the probability of retention, and the smaller the probability of being simplified. This is the same as drawing a single sample from a multinomial distribution, which was implemented using the roulette wheel selection method [16]. A proportion of the wheel is assigned to each of the possible selections based on the local terrain knowledge of points within the subregions. Then a random selection is made similar to how the roulette wheel is rotated.

Figure 2. TKPCS algorithm workflow.

C. Evaluation methods and test area

We compared the TKPCS method with the revised random and curvature methods that are also limited by grids. Metrics, including the surface area loss of the modelled terrain based on triangular irregular networks (TINs), the root mean square error (RMSE) and mean absolute error (MAE) of the grid based DEMs (Grid-DEMs), and the average slope information entropy of the simplified points, were used for comparing the simplified results. The reference data of the metrics is generated from raw point

clouds. Each validation method was carried out at reduction ratios of 90%, 95% and 99% and grid sizes of 1 to 5 m to verify the accuracy and stability of our method. The test area is sampled from a watershed in the Loess Plateau. Point clouds in the test area was generated using photogrammetric methods with approximately 30 points per square metre (Fig. 1(f, g, h)).

III. RESULTS

A. Simplified point clouds using different methods

In contrast to the simplified points of the revised curvature and random methods, the distribution of the TKPCS method's simplified points exhibits two key characteristics (Fig. 4(a)). First, regions with complex terrain are where the TKPCS method's simplified points are most found. Second, the TKPCS method retains a rather uniform distribution of points. Furthermore, our method can retain more terrain feature points from the parts of the test area (Fig. 4(b, c)). In addition, the average slope entropy of the TKPCS method's simplified points is higher than that of the other methods (Fig. 5(a)). This implies a higher slope dispersion of the simplified points of the TKPCS method, indicating that the simplified points of the TKPCS method can retain more terrain information.

B. Terrain modelling with the simplified point clouds

From the perspective of generated Grid-DEMs, first, the TKPCS method achieves high frequencies in low difference (0~0.2) with the reference data Fig. 3. Second, the TKPCS method generally achieves smaller MAE values (Fig. 5(b)). In terms of generated TINs, (Fig. 5(c)) shows that the surface area loss of the TKPCS method is smaller overall than that of the other methods. This means that terrain surfaces (e.g., TINs) constructed using the TKPCS method's simplified points are closer to the original terrain surfaces than those of the other methods. The above validation shows that the TKPCS method outperforms the other methods in terrain modelling.

Figure 3. The difference frequency of Grid-DEMs at 99% reduction ratio.

VI. REFERENCES

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Figure 4. Simplified points and their partial enlargements.

Figure 5. (a), (b), and (c) are average slope entropy, MAE, and surface area loss, respectively, with multiple reduction ratios and grid sizes.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The comparisons demonstrate the TKPCS method's superior performance in terrain modelling. Furthermore, the simplified points of the TKPCS method are mostly distributed in terrain features and retain more terrain information.

V. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was supported by the National Science Foundation of China under Grant [41930102]; National Key Research and Development Program of China under Grant [2021YFB3900901]; Priority Academic Program Development of Jiangsu Higher Education Institutions under Grant [164320H116].